

24-hour Urine Calcium Predicts Reduced Fracture Incidence and Improved BMD After Surgery for Primary Hyperparathyroidism

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Supplemental Table 1. ICD-8/9/10 codes defining anatomical fracture site.

Fracture site	ICD-8	ICD-9	ICD-10
Vertebral	80500/10/21/31/90/91, 80600/10/21/22/31/32/ 90/91/92	8050–5, 8060–5	S12, S220–1, S320, M485
Rib	80700/10/90	8070–1	S223–4
Proximal humerus	81200/10/90	8120–1	S422
Distal radius	81300/10/42/52/90/92	8134–5	S525–6
Upper extremity incl. shoulder	810–1, 81221/31/42/52/91/92, 81321/31/63/73/91/93	810–1, 8122–5	S420–1, S423–9, S520–4, S527–9
Hand	814–7	814–7	S62
Pelvic	80542/52/92, 80643/53/93, 808	8056–7, 8066–7, 808	S321–8
Hip	820	820	S720–2
Lower extremity	821–4	821–4	S723–9, S82
Foot	825–6	825–6	S92
Other	80564/74/94, 80664/74/94, 80721/31/42/52/91/92, 809, 818–9, 827–8	8072–3 8075–6, 809, 818–9, 827–8	S222, S225–9, T02, T08, T10, T12, T142

Supplemental Table 2. Temporal trends in patient characteristics, n (percent), mean $\pm$ SD or median (IQR). Nonparametric test for trend across ordered groups.¹

	1989–1996	1997–2004	2005–2013	<i>p</i>
Male sex, <i>n</i>	124 (22.3)	120 (24.0)	393 (22.3)	0.966
Age, years	64.1 $\pm$ 13.2	67.9 $\pm$ 13.5	63.6 $\pm$ 13.1	0.163
Total calcium, mg/dL	11.1 $\pm$ 0.831	11.2 $\pm$ 0.780	10.8 $\pm$ 0.693	<0.001
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d	186 (124–256)	180 (108–244)	168 (111–257)	0.186
PTH, pg/mL	78 (60–110)	100 (74–140)	94 (75–130)	<0.001
Adenoma weight, g	0.63 (0.34–1.32)	0.63 (0.35–1.09)	0.67 (0.35–1.38)	0.817

Supplemental Table 3. Univariable mixed-effects Poisson regression, patients only. Available cases.

Major osteoporotic fracture	Preoperatively		Postoperatively	
	IRR (CI 95%)	p	IRR (CI 95%)	p
Total calcium, mg/dL Δ 1 year	0.58 (0.35–0.98)	0.042	1.35 (0.89–2.04) 0.87 (0.58–1.31)	0.162 0.507
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d Δ 1 year	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.760	0.99 (0.99–1.00) 1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.012 0.088
PTH, pg/mL Δ 1 year	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.897	1.00 (1.00–1.00) 1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.720 0.959
Osteocalcin, ng/mL Δ 1 year	0.98 (0.96–1.01)	0.225	1.00 (0.99–1.02) 1.00 (0.98–1.02)	0.802 0.960
25-OH Vitamin D, ng/mL Δ 1 year	0.94 (0.89–1.00)	0.057	0.96 (0.92–1.01) 1.02 (0.97–1.06)	0.086 0.507
Creatinine, pg/mL Δ 1 year	0.32 (0.07–1.60)	0.166	5.24 (1.89–14.5) 5.90 (0.64–54.6)	0.001 0.118
Iohexol clearance, mL/min/1.73 m ² Δ 1 year	0.97 (0.94–1.00)	0.030	0.95 (0.93–0.98) 1.03 (0.97–1.09)	<0.001 0.331
BMD femoral neck, g/cm ² Δ 1 year improved (≥2.77%)	0.01 (0.00–0.34)	0.009	0.00 (0.00–0.00) 1.08 (0.00–36,800) 1.57 (0.69–3.58)	<0.001 0.989 0.284
BMD L2–L4, g/cm ² Δ 1 year improved (≥2.77%)	0.16 (0.02–1.22)	0.077	0.08 (0.01–0.49) 0.05 (0.00–4.05) 0.77 (0.36–1.65)	0.007 0.184 0.507
BMD radius, g/cm ² Δ 1 year improved (≥2.77%)	0.00 (0.00–0.10)	0.004	0.00 (0.00–0.09) 0.06 (0.00–14,300) 0.41 (0.08–2.09)	0.002 0.655 0.286
Osteoporosis preoperatively	1.73 (0.85–3.50)	0.128	1.42 (0.75–2.70)	0.285
Multiglandular disease	0.43 (0.09–2.02)	0.287	0.60 (0.17–2.17)	0.438
Adenoma on histology	1.12 (0.29–4.33)	0.869	0.83 (0.26–2.67)	0.756
Adenoma weight, g	1.00 (0.80–1.24)	0.990	0.93 (0.75–1.16)	0.506

Supplemental Table 4. Multivariable mixed-effects Poisson regression, patients only. Adjusted for sex, age (in 10-year bands), and period of surgery (1989–1996, 1997–2004, 2005–2013).

Major osteoporotic fracture	N	Preoperatively		Postoperatively	
		IRR (CI 95%)	p	IRR (CI 95%)	p
Total calcium, mg/dL	702	0.53 (0.31–0.89)	0.017	1.09 (0.74–1.61)	0.673
Δ 1 year	643			0.97 (0.65–1.44)	0.878
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d	502	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.411	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.309
Δ 1 year	413			1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.405
PTH, pg/mL	668	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.535	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.339
Δ 1 year	597			1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.634
Osteocalcin, ng/mL	301	0.98 (0.95–1.01)	0.149	1.00 (0.98–1.02)	0.983
Δ 1 year	266			1.00 (0.98–1.02)	0.888
25-OH Vitamin D, ng/mL	563	0.94 (0.88–1.01)	0.079	0.97 (0.93–1.02)	0.212
Δ 1 year	367			1.01 (0.97–1.05)	0.627
BMD femoral neck, g/cm ²	512	0.17 (0.00–9.78)	0.389	0.00 (0.00–0.11)	0.002
Δ 1 year, g/cm ²	442			11.0 (0.00–148,000)	0.622
improved (≥2.77%)				1.69 (0.78–3.69)	0.187
BMD L2–L4, g/cm ²	545	0.30 (0.04–2.43)	0.257	0.25 (0.04–1.40)	0.115
Δ 1 year, g/cm ²	472			0.01 (0.00–3.71)	0.124
improved (≥2.77%)				0.85 (0.41–1.73)	0.645
BMD radius, g/cm ²	421	0.00 (0.00–0.63)	0.035	0.01 (0.00–1.90)	0.087
Δ 1 year, g/cm ²	360			0.06 (0.00–39,400)	0.679
improved (≥2.77%)				0.41 (0.08–2.02)	0.271
Multiglandular disease	658	0.39 (0.09–1.81)	0.231	0.53 (0.16–1.72)	0.289
Adenoma weight, g	633	1.04 (0.84–1.29)	0.719	1.01 (0.83–1.23)	0.932

Supplemental Table 5. Logistic regression of significantly improved bone mineral density ($\geq 2.77\%$), patients. Multivariable regressions for each predictor adjusted for sex, age >50 years, and period of surgery (1989–1996, 1997–2004, 2005–2013).

	N	Univariable regression		Multivariable regression	
		OR (CI 95%)	p	OR (CI 95%)	p
BMD femoral neck,					
Total calcium, mg/dL	440	1.72 (1.27–2.34)	<0.001	1.77 (1.30–2.42)	<0.001
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d	341	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.029	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.093
PTH, pg/mL	432	1.01 (1.00–1.01)	0.001	1.01 (1.00–1.01)	<0.001
25-OH Vitamin D, ng/mL	364	0.97 (0.94–1.00)	0.028	0.97 (0.94–1.00)	0.027
Osteocalcin, ng/mL	244	1.01 (1.00–1.02)	0.030	1.01 (1.00–1.02)	0.026
Multiglandular disease	437	0.98 (0.50–1.92)	0.952	1.01 (0.51–1.99)	0.974
Adenoma weight, g	399	1.22 (1.06–1.42)	0.007	1.22 (1.05–1.41)	0.008
BMD L2–L4					
Total calcium, mg/dL	470	1.36 (1.03–1.81)	0.031	1.38 (1.04–1.84)	0.026
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d	358	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.008	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.011
PTH, pg/mL	462	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.010	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.009
25-OH Vitamin D, ng/mL	394	0.99 (0.97–1.02)	0.431	0.99 (0.97–1.02)	0.466
Osteocalcin, ng/mL	259	1.01 (1.00–1.03)	0.017	1.01 (1.00–1.03)	0.016
Multiglandular disease	467	1.04 (0.54–1.99)	0.906	1.05 (0.54–2.01)	0.892
Adenoma weight, g	426	1.05 (0.94–1.18)	0.373	1.05 (0.94–1.18)	0.375
BMD distal radius					
Total calcium, mg/dL	358	1.82 (1.26–2.64)	0.001	1.82 (1.25–2.64)	0.002
24-hour urine calcium, mg/d	276	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.546	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.509
PTH, pg/mL	352	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.009	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.008
25-OH Vitamin D, ng/mL	289	0.98 (0.95–1.02)	0.262	0.98 (0.94–1.01)	0.229
Osteocalcin, ng/mL	240	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.248	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.256
Multiglandular disease	355	1.07 (0.46–2.48)	0.870	1.05 (0.45–2.44)	0.909
Adenoma weight, g	326	1.15 (1.00–1.31)	0.049	1.14 (1.00–1.31)	0.050

References

1. Cuzick J. A Wilcoxon-type test for trend. *Stat Med.* 1985;4(1):87-90.